

11TH CONFERENCE FOR YOUNG SCIENTISTS IN CERAMICS

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Satellite event:
ESR COST IC1208 Workshop

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

October 21-24, 2105
Faculty of Technology
Novi Sad, Serbia

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ESR Workshop, COST IC1208

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**October 21-24, 2015
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INFLUENCE OF DENTAL COMPOSITE CORE MATERIAL ON BIOMECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF PREMOLARS RESTORED WITH A ZIRCONIA FULL CROWN: A FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

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Endodontically treated teeth with severe tooth tissue damage are often restored with a fiber-reinforced polymer composite post (FRC), a polymer-ceramic composite core and a full crown. Many current studies aim at defining what choice of reconstructive material would have the most optimal influence on the remaining tooth tissues, as well as on the longevity of the restoration.

A very useful method for this kind of analysis is the finite element analysis (FEA), which is a mathematical method of calculating the values and the distribution of stress and strain in complex three-dimensional (3D) models. The aim of this study was to examine the influence of dental polymer-ceramic composite core material on biomechanical properties of premolars restored with a zirconia full crown and a FRC post.

On a 3D tooth model created in SolidWorks 2014 software (Dassault Systemes SolidWorks Corp, USA), based on Computed Tomography (CT) scans of an extracted maxillary second premolar, the influence of two core materials (Gradia posterior, GC, Japan and Filtek Z250, 3M, ESPE, EUA) was tested.

The results showed that in the case where the core material with lower modulus of elasticity was used (Gradia posterior), lower von Mises stresses were distributed to the core itself, but they were found to be higher on the post and the post cement. This could indicate that a core material of much lower modulus of elasticity than the zirconia crown, transfers the stresses to the tissues below it, while the stiffer core material (Filtek Z250 in this study) might be able to receive a part of the generated stresses during mastication. The use of a stiffer core material could be favourable for the longevity of tooth tissues and the restoration.

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